

Tricyanomethanide Complexes of Oxomolybdenum(V)

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Manuscript received 20 March 1995, revised 10 January 1996, accepted 24 March 1996

Pyridinium salt of pentachlorooxomolybdenum(V) reacts with potassium tricyanomethanide in non-aqueous medium to produce $\text{pyH}[\text{MoOpy}(\text{C}(\text{CN})_3)\text{Cl}_3]$. Different derivatives of the species have been prepared under varied condition. Under no condition more than one pseudo-halide ion could be introduced into the coordination zone.

The tricyanomethanide ion, $\text{C}(\text{CN})_3^-$ is an established pseudo-halide with a resonating D_{3h} planar structure in which the negative charge is preferentially located on cyano nitrogen as

The anion is a potential ligand coordinating either through N or C and forms complexes with various *d*- or *f*-block metal ions¹. There are reports² of reaction of Mo^{V} with $\text{C}(\text{CN})_3^-$ in DMF or MeCN medium but no solid products have been isolated. The present communication describes the preparation and characterisation of the following two series of solid complexes formed from reaction of Mo^{V}

and $\text{C}(\text{CN})_3^-$: electrolytic $\text{R}[\text{MoOpy}(\text{C}(\text{CN})_3)\text{Cl}_3]$ ($\text{R}^+ = \text{pyH}^+, \text{Ag}^+, \text{Me}_4\text{N}^+, \text{Cs}^+$, diimine H^+ (dipy H^+ , *o*-phen H^+)) and non-electrolytic $[\text{MoOpy}_2(\text{C}(\text{CN})_3)\text{Cl}_2]$ and $[\text{MoO}(\text{diimine})(\text{C}(\text{CN})_3)\text{Cl}_2]$.

Results and Discussion

The elemental analyses of the salts and their molar conductance values (in water/DMSO) (Table 1) correspond to 1 : 1 electrolyte with the common complex anion, $[\text{MoOpy}(\text{C}(\text{CN})_3)\text{Cl}_3]^-$. The parent pyH^+ salt is freely soluble in water and in contrast to known halooxomolybdenum(V) species, the complex is quite stable. The conductance as well as visible spectrum of the solution remain unchanged for a long time. Thus it appears that the coordinated pseudo-halide $\text{C}(\text{CN})_3^-$ offers both redox and hydrolytic stability to the described complex. Any attempt to isolate the free acid was unsuccessful due to decomposition. However, dilute aqueous solution of the free acid is stable for indefinite period. It was titrated pH-metrically and a standard titration curve of a weak acid ($\text{p}K_a$, 4.0) was

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL AND PHYSICAL DATA OF THE COMPLEXES

Compd./ (Colour)	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd.)					Mol. cond.** $\Omega^{-1} \text{ cm}^2$	μ_{eff} (B.M.) at 299 K
	C	H	N	Mo	Cl		
$\text{pyH}[\text{MoOpyLCl}_3]$ (Emerald green)	36.23 (35.95)	2.31 2.35	14.30 14.97	21.09 20.54	22.61 22.78)	118.5 ^a	1.82
$\text{Ag}[\text{MoOpyLCl}_3]$ (Leaf green)	21.23 (21.80)	1.59 1.01	11.68 11.30)	19.33 19.37)	20.37 21.49)	38.3 ^b	1.71
$\text{Me}_4\text{N}[\text{MoOpyLCl}_3]$ (Green)	34.23 (33.80)	2.78 3.68	15.68 15.17)	19.88 20.80)	22.71 23.01)	37.4 ^b	1.69
$\text{Cs}[\text{MoOpyLCl}_3]$ (Leaf green)	20.14 (20.75)	1.98 0.96	10.15 10.75)	17.78 18.44)	20.20 20.46)	37.9 ^b	1.74
$\text{dipyH}[\text{MoOpyLCl}_3]$ (Yellow)	39.51 (41.95)	3.09 2.58	14.98 15.46)	17.11 17.66)	19.03 19.60)	36.7 ^b	1.72
<i>o</i> -phenH[MoOpyLCl_3] (Emerald green)	43.95 (44.40)	2.96 2.47	14.05 14.78)	17.43 16.92)	19.07 18.77)	36.9 ^b	1.70
$[\text{MoO}(\text{dipy})\text{LCl}_2]$ (Brown)	38.80 (39.16)	2.32 1.87	15.81 16.32)	21.93 22.38)	16.28 16.55)	6.5 ^b	1.64
$[\text{MoO}(\textit{o}\text{-phen})\text{LCl}_2]$ (Brown)	41.81 (42.38)	2.01 1.77	15.05 15.45)	20.98 21.19)	15.29 15.67)	6.2 ^b	1.75
$[\text{MoO}(\text{py})_2\text{LCl}_2]$ (Brown)	38.12 (38.98)	2.65 2.32	15.92 16.24)	21.89 22.27)	16.36 16.47)	5.3 ^b	1.74

*L = $\text{C}(\text{CN})_3^-$. **Solvent : ^awater : ^bDMSO.

obtained upto neutralisation (1 eqv. of base). The complex anion decomposes thereafter in excess alkali in an unknown manner.

Thermal analysis of $\text{pyH}[\text{MoOpy}\{\text{C}(\text{CN})_3\}\text{Cl}_3]$ was carried out in argon atmosphere. The TG curve shows a gradual loss in weight (9%) with a small break at 300° . This can be accounted for the loss of HCl with simultaneous formation of nonelectrolytic product,

The observed weight-loss is slightly greater than required (7.8%) by the above reaction and it is possibly due to simultaneous oxidation caused by the trace oxygen present. The HCl elimination was further confirmed by isothermal heating of the pyridinium salt at $260 \pm 5^\circ$ in inert CO_2 atmosphere, and both the gaseous and residual products were analysed. The non-electrolytic complexes were prepared in this manner. The TG was continued upto 800° and a gradual net weight-loss of 17% was observed but could not be accounted for any single definite reaction.

The magnetic susceptibility values of all the compounds correspond to d^1 spin moment of MoO^{3+} unit. The average μ_{eff} of 1.72 B.M. is a clear indication of negligible orbital contribution and absence of any metal-metal bonding proving the mononuclear nature of the complex. The esr spectrum of $\text{pyH}[\text{MoOpy}\{\text{C}(\text{CN})_3\}\text{Cl}_3]$ (in acetone at room temperature) consists of a strong central line due to resonance of molecules with even mass Mo nuclei ($I = 0$) flanked by six hyperfine lines due to interaction between the unpaired electron and the Mo^{95} and Mo^{97} nuclei ($I = 5/2$). The anisotropic $\langle g \rangle$ value and the $^{95,97}\text{Mo}$ hyperfine parameter $\langle A \rangle$ are 1.964 and $46.67 \times 10^{-4} \text{ cm}^{-1}$ respectively, and these corroborate the presence of mononuclear Mo^{V} species in solution.

The electronic spectral bands of $\text{pyH}[\text{MoOpy}\{\text{C}(\text{CN})_3\}\text{Cl}_3]$ (in water) can be explained on the basis of strong tetragonal d -distortion of the octahedral oxomolybdenum(V) species. The actual symmetry is still lower than the tetragonal. Two crystal field transition bands at $13\,333$ and $22\,421 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ are assigned to transitions ${}^2E \leftarrow {}^2B_2$ and ${}^2B_1 \leftarrow {}^2B_2$ respectively. A third medium intensity band at $27\,777 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ due to ${}^2A_1 \leftarrow {}^2B_2$ transition is observed as a shoulder on an intense Cl...Mo charge transfer band. A relatively intense band at $37\,037 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ may be assigned as $M \leftarrow L$ charge transfer from π -bonding oxygen orbitals to the half filled B_2 level. The spectra of other salts were measured in DMSO which give similar pattern indicating the presence of a common complex anion but measurements could not be made beyond $25\,000 \text{ cm}^{-1}$. The ir spectra of

all the compounds give the characteristic $\nu_{\text{Mo=O}}$ band at 980 cm^{-1} while any Mo—O—Mo vibration band was absent indicating the monomeric nature of the compounds. The strong band at $2\,176 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ was identified as $\nu_{\text{C=N}}$ arising from the pseudo-halide ligand. Characteristic ir bands of pyridine were present.

Experimental

For analysis of the complexes, Mo^{VI} sulphide was precipitated from solution after decomposition of the compounds with alkali peroxide. Cl was determined gravimetrically as AgCl after removal of Mo as MoS_3 . The precipitated MoS_3 was oxidised to Mo^{VI} by Br_2 -water and Mo was determined by the reported method³ using Jones reductor. C, H and N were determined by microanalysis.

Magnetic susceptibility was measured with a Gouy balance at a field strength of 9.1×10^3 Oe. Conductance measurement was done by a Systronic's conductance bridge. Ir spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 782 spectrophotometer, electronic spectra on a Cary 2390 spectrophotometer and esr spectra on a Varian E112 spectrometer.

Preparations : $\text{KC}(\text{CN})_3$ was prepared in the reported method⁴. $(\text{pyH})_2[\text{MoOCl}_5]$ was prepared⁵ by reducing Mo^{VI} oxide in HCl with HI followed by crystallisation of $(\text{pyH})^+$ salt with pyH^+Cl^- . The primary compound, the pyridinium salt, $\text{pyH}[\text{MoOpy}\{\text{C}(\text{CN})_3\}\text{Cl}_3]$ was prepared by refluxing $(\text{pyH})_2[\text{MoOCl}_5]$ (0.5 g) with ethanolic solution (25 ml) of $\text{KC}(\text{CN})_3$ (0.6 g) for 2 h. The resulting green solid was washed with ethanol and vacuum-dried (yield 0.6 g). The Ag^+ , Me_4N^+ and Cs^+ salts were prepared in quantitative yield by metathesis of $\text{pyH}[\text{MoOpy}\{\text{C}(\text{CN})_3\}\text{Cl}_3]$ (0.25 g) in water (20 ml) with 5 ml aqueous AgNO_3 (0.1 g), Me_4NBr (0.091 g) and CsCl (0.099 g) respectively. For preparation of diimine salts, free aqueous complex acid, $\text{H}[\text{MoOpy}\{\text{C}(\text{CN})_3\}\text{Cl}_3]$ was obtained from the pyridinium salt (0.3 g in 10 ml) using Dowex 50 cation-exchanger and subsequently neutralised with respective diimine (0.2 g) to obtain green powder, after filtration and washing with ethanol.

The non-electrolytic compounds were prepared by isothermal heating of the salts (0.1 g) of heterocyclic bases (230° for pyH^+ and 250° for diimine H^+) in dry CO_2 atmosphere followed by washing the product with ethanol and drying.

Acknowledgement

The authors offer their sincere gratitude to Prof. P. Bandyopadhyay and Prof. B. K. Sen, of this Department, for their valuable suggestions and encouragement.

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